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Oscillating Wave Surge Converter**

Collaborative project

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Authors	

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Approved (Coordinator)	Ilpo Honkanen (Hydroll)	21.12.2021

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

MegaRoller is a Horizon 2020 project focusing on how to improve European Ocean Wave Energy devices, specifically by developing a Power Take-off unit able to increase the output from the few 100 kW range to a full 1 MW range. The project has generated extensive know-how in the area of PTO design and control systems and contributed to the decrease of levelized cost of energy (LCOE) of next-generation OWSC devices.

The purpose of this final dissemination report is to outline the dissemination activities that have taken place in the consortium during the project and the activities set out in the corresponding dissemination plan. This document therefore contains the original plan (D6.2) as well as the report on the activities taken place in the duration of the project from May 2018 (Dissemination report I) to the final month in December 2021 covered by this report.

Dissemination activities are done in order to maximize the impact, take-up, visibility, and credibility of the project. This report addresses the purpose of dissemination, what has been disseminated to whom, how and when.

The findings from the project have been disseminated to relevant stakeholders throughout the duration of the project, although the pandemic made a clear impact on the activities in the final years. Dissemination usually takes place using publications and conferences, however the originally planned dedicated workshops and scientific meetings was replaced with digital activities.

There is a strong link between the communication and the dissemination activities in any H2020 project. The communication report will, therefore, be linked and for certain activities – overlap in purpose and content with this dissemination report. The original plans, and the updates in the dissemination report are included and updated in this final report on dissemination.

1 DISSEMINATION OVERVIEW

1.1 Introduction

Wave power represents a considerable opportunity for clean renewable energy supply. The potential of supplying 10-15% of EU power demand by 2050, which can reduce EU dependency on energy imports, create thousands of jobs, and contribute to diversification and decarbonisation of the economy. This project focused on oscillating wave surge converters (OWSCs), a type of wave power technology that is designed to absorb wave energy through the horizontal motion of the prime mover. This deliverable presents the original plan as well as the activities performed during the project for the dissemination of the results to the ocean energy community.

1.2 Dissemination objectives

Dissemination is a key activity in MegaRoller to increase the impact of the project. The overall objective for dissemination is to maximize the impact, take-up, visibility, and credibility of the project. In particular, the specific objectives are:

- Transfer knowledge of the MegaRoller concept through relevant educational resources and the organisation of workshops to relevant stakeholders, authorities, users, suppliers, and potential owners of wave energy systems.
- Design, develop and update a dedicated MegaRoller website with relevant material suited for dissemination (reports, white papers, publications, data, blogs, newsletters, etc.).
- Support the development of a plan for the exploitation of the key outcomes of the MegaRoller project beyond the life of the project by informing of its content.
- The priorities of the dissemination activities of the MegaRoller project are to promote not only the project results but also Wave Energy as a viable and future energy source in abundance in Europe and around the world.

This way, the MegaRoller project will obtain the attention and support of not only to those who benefit from its advanced technology, but also those who are interested in the topic of wave energy in academia and industry. Dissemination and communication activities are often concerted actions and the D6.1 Communication Plan supplements many of the outreach activities towards relevant stakeholders, in particular society at large and public authorities.

1.3 Dissemination Strategy

With the objective to ensure an effective dissemination of knowledge during the project and beyond, the MegaRoller Consortium has established a Dissemination strategy that is based on the guidelines proposed by the H2020 online manual. The following summarizes the dissemination framework set up for the MegaRoller project that is suggested in H2020 online manual:

- What dissemination outputs will be created in MegaRoller? See section 2.
- Why dissemination outputs will be created? What is the target that MegaRoller would like to achieve through the dissemination of results? See section 1.2 Objectives.
- Who are the stakeholders of MegaRoller results? See section 4.
- How to disseminate the results? Which channels and tools should be implemented to disseminate the results? See section 5.
- Where will the outputs be made available during and after the project and who does the specific

dissemination activities? See section 6

- When will the dissemination activities happen? See section 8
- What dissemination activities have been done since M1. See section 9.

These frameworks are used to establish the dissemination plan. In the following, each point mentioned above is covered in more detail.

2 WHAT WILL BE DISSEMINATED

The project will disseminate open results from the MegaRoller project. During the project, the focus will be on a combination of continuous dissemination and collaboration with relevant stakeholders to develop a PTO system that will form the core of a new group of European Wave Energy devices. These will, in turn, contribute to enabling a European leadership in Wave Energy and to support the knowledge and competence needed in the industry.

Dissemination can take place in many settings and through various channels. In the following the most common dissemination materials are summarized in separate categories.

2.1 Website

The main goal of the [MegaRoller](#) website is to establish a widespread channel to disseminate and access information around the EU MegaRoller project, activities, and results. The target group is a wide set of the stakeholders i.e., Private industry, the scientific community, public authorities, and society at large. Visitors will find public deliverables produced during the project. The website provides access to internal pages, which is restricted to partners in the project, this mainly aims to facilitate the exchange of documents between the partners, but it will be a repository of material that can be relevant for all the partners.

MEET THE WORK PACKAGE LEADERS

Figure 2-1 Homepage of MegaRoller

2.2 Scientific publications

Articles in peer-reviewed journals are scientific publications. According to H2020 Open Access Mandate, the MegaRoller project will ensure open access to all scientific publications. Open access refers to the practice of providing online access to scientific information that is free of charge to the end-user and reusable. There are two ways of achieving open access:

- **Green open access:** the author deposits the final peer-reviewed manuscript (not the published version) in an online repository. Most journals request an embargo period before the manuscript can be open access. The H2020 Open Access mandate accepts a maximum of 6 months embargo.
- **Gold open access:** the article is immediately published in open access mode, either by an open-access journal or a hybrid journal. Gold open access usually involves Article Processing Charges (APC). The APC should be covered by the corresponding author's institution and are eligible for reimbursement during the project period.

The author decides where to publish. The scientific journals relevant to the MegaRoller project are listed below.

Table 2-1 List of relevant scientific journals

Title	ISSN	Scopus Cite Score	Type of journal	APC ¹	Embargo
Renewable Energy	0960-1481	5,38	Subscription/Hybrid	USD 3000	24 months
International Journal of Neural Systems	1793-6462	5,15	Subscription/Hybrid	Depend on the subject area/ length of the article	12 months
PLoS Computational Biology	1553-734X	4,49	OA	USD 2350	
Frontiers in Marine Science Journal of Marine Science and Engineering	2296-77452077-1312	2,89	OAOA	US1900 CHF 350	
Journal of Ocean Engineering and Marine Energy	2198-6452	1,85	Subscription/Hybrid	USD 3000	12 months
PLoS Computational Biology	1553-734X	4,49	OA	USD 2350	
Renewable Energy	0960-1481	5,38	Subscription/Hybrid	USD 3000	24 months

All scientific publications will be uploaded to an open repository. The MegaRoller project will use Zenodo as its repository both for publications and research data. A [MegaRoller community in Zenodo](#) has been established. Scientific publications and underlying data will be linked using persisting identifiers.

We assume that new demands on Open Access as expressed in Coalition S² do not affect the MegaRoller project, but the project nevertheless aims to publish in high-quality open access journals or platforms where they exist.

Open Access to research data is referred to in D6.4 Data management plan and reports.

¹ APC refer to the costs of immediate open access to articles (Gold open access). Green open access can be considered if the journal embargo period doesn't exceed 6 months.

² [cOAlition S : Making Open Access a reality by 2020](#)

2.3 Scientific presentations and industry events/conferences

Several of the industry partners will promote their activity and possible innovations made in industry events. There will also be participation and presentation of results from MegaRoller in scientific conferences. See Table 5-2 for a detailed list of events.

2.4 Standardization work

Standards can be a powerful tool and an important basis for development. A standard can set certain limitations and requirements that have to be fulfilled or otherwise a unit or system cannot be employed in the market as certifications, in general, will require compliance with standards. Participation in standardization is a way of disseminating the practical results of the work in the MegaRoller as the standards bodies often lack relevant data to support the standardization work.

2.5 Tutorials and educational materials

As a measure to reach a wider audience, including academia and students, technical memos and tutorials including whitepapers will be considered for release through the web page.

2.6 Dissemination reports

Two dissemination reports are planned to be issued at months 18 and 36 respectively, summarizing the activities in Dissemination throughout this period and – if relevant – update on details on planned dissemination. Dissemination plan and report are public deliverables.

2.7 Project Video

A project video is planned to be made during the project. The purpose of the video is to inform the broader audience about the project concept, its goals and possible impacts on society. The format (animations vs real images) etc will be decided later. The video will have a format and length that makes it suitable for wide distribution, including channels like YouTube. Also, the deliverable D6.1 Communication plan refers to these types of media use.

2.8 Other

When relevant, the MegaRoller consortium will consider if there is an ample opportunity to join forces with another ongoing project, including infrastructure promoting actions. Another action that can benefit from the interaction is the newly started COST action on marine energies, CA 17105, which will cover several aspects of relevance to MegaRoller. Several of the member countries will contribute and the consortium is also represented in the management committee of this cost action.

3 TO WHOM: STAKEHOLDERS IN MEGAROLLER

With the view to have a far-reaching impact in MegaRoller, the dissemination strategy will encompass all stakeholders of the value network. The main stakeholders are:

- Private industry: Utilities, Subsystem suppliers, Engineering, Procurement and Construction companies, Investors, insurers
- Scientific Community: Wave energy researchers, Environmental impact researchers
- Public authorities: National and regional authorities, European Commission
- Society at large: Media and general public

An overview is shown in Table 3-1.

Table 3-1 Overview of stakeholder issues that are addressed in MegaRoller

Category	Target Audience	Why	What's in it for this audience? Issues.
Private Industry	Utilities	There is a lack of practical experience and performance data collected from open sea deployment, preventing industrial stakeholders to develop full-scale arrays	Learn from practical experience and collected performance data to plan for grid integration, operation, and maintenance of wave energy plants
	Subsystem Suppliers		Learn from practical experience and collected performance data in order to improve the performance, reliability, and survivability of subsystems
	Engineering, Procurement and Construction companies	The development of the sector depends on how confident the investors are that the ocean energy devices will perform reliably and produce the expected output for their devices	Learn from practical experience and collected performance data to plan for the construction of wave energy plants
	Investors Insurers		Produce LCOE models and investment business cases based on the data collected in the project
Scientific Community	Wave energy researchers	Models that have been developed only consider the first-generation wave power plants	Access for scientific data and publications of second-generation wave energy performance
	Environmental impact researchers		
Public Authorities	National and Regional authorities	Public funding authorities must use stage-gate evaluation to allocate funding effectively	Provide a framework to address environmental and social impacts and a case example of a wave energy converter development
	European Commission		
Society at large	Media	Media has so far provided more coverage to more mature sectors (wind and solar)	Provide valuable scientific data to raise awareness about the enormous potential of ocean energy
	General Public		

4 HOW: DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

There is a close link to the communication activities in the project covered in the deliverable D6.1: Communication Plan and the subsequent reports. While the communication activities' main goal is to inform about the action, the project goals, and overall scientific content, the core goal of the dissemination activities is to promote the results of the action. However, some channels, including blogs, press releases, action/project web page all play a part in the promotion of the action itself and results and there is naturally overlap in some activities and descriptions as both tasks will include information about the action as well as the results. Table 4-1 shows an overview of the planned activities in MegaRoller related to the dissemination.

Table 4-1 Overview of general dissemination activities during MegaRoller

Purpose	Activity	Stakeholder/target group
Share results in order to the industry to learn from practical experience and collected performance data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Articles in industry-specific magazines and newsletters Internal channels such as company magazines/conferences Industry events such as exhibition and conferences Research blogs and newsletters* Press releases* Website* Video* 	Private industry
Share results openly in order to the scientific community to access a reference testing facility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Peer-reviewed articles in open access journals Posters and presentations at relevant scientific conferences Scientific workshops Research blogs and newsletters* Website* Video * 	Scientific community
Raise awareness about the enormous potential of ocean energy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Workshops Involvement in relevant EU implementation plans Blogs and newsletters* Video Social media* 	Public authorities
Raise awareness about the enormous potential of ocean energy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> For all details see deliverable D6.1: Communication Plan 	Society at large

*For more details see deliverable D6.1: Communication Plan.

5 WHERE: DISSEMINATION EVENTS AND ARENAS

Organization and participation of events, which will be thematically related to MegaRoller, will be a part of the dissemination activities. The events include relevant conferences, seminars, workshops, etc. The main goal of these events is to increase the visibility of MegaRoller results and facilitate knowledge sharing that can accelerate the development of the wave energy industry. Moreover, with the participation of such events MegaRoller project aims to:

- Exchange experience on developing the new PTO with other working groups in the field to join forces and converge into a more standardized solution for wave energy.
- Disseminate the fundamental knowledge, and methodologies developed during the project within the scientific community.
- Facilitate the exchange of standards/guidelines within industrial partners that can help to accelerate a more successful commercial, and non-commercial, exploitation of the project outcomes.

Dissemination results will be carried out through several events during the project. These include events organized by the MegaRoller project, such as MegaRoller workshops to introduce the MegaRoller PTO and demonstrate its operation in the test bench, and several presentations in relevant conferences within the different areas of interest to the project.

The stakeholder workshops are planned to last one working day and will include presentations, a tour of facilities and Q&A sessions. In these sessions, the stakeholders would learn about the project, the technology and the potential benefits of MegaRoller to their respective organisations. A first stakeholder workshop is planned in Month 28 and will focus on renewable energy technology developers while a workshop planned in Month 32 will target potential customers, members of standards working groups and government representatives and press. Table 5-1 summarises the expected impact and stakeholders in the MegaRoller workshops. *In the summer of 2021, it was decided that these stakeholder workshops had to be cancelled due to covid-19 and were replaced with video informational material.*

Table 5-1 MegaRoller workshops

Venue	Expected Stakeholder	Exp. attendance
Workshop at AW-Energy facilities I	Renewable energy technology developers interested in technology transfer	50-100
Workshop at AW-Energy facilities II	Target potential customers, members of standards working groups and government representatives and press.	50-100

Demonstrations at the AW-Energy test facilities as well as presentations to the stakeholders would be a natural part of the full-day workshops.

Table 5-2 summarises the potential events that MegaRoller partners could attend during the project period.

Table 5-2 MegaRoller participation events

Venue	Partner involved	Expected Stakeholders	Exp. attendance
MegaRoller workshop	AW-Energy	Renewable energy technology developers	100
MegaRoller workshop	AW-Energy	Potential customers, members of standards working groups and government representatives and press.	100
World Energy Congress	AW-Energy	Key decision-makers such as Industry developers, Policymakers, and Investors.	10,000
The Future of Energy Summit	AW-Energy	Key decision-makers such as Industry developers, Policymakers, and Investors.	2,000
The Energy Executive Forum	AW-Energy	Key decision-makers such as Industry developers, Policymakers, and Investors.	2,000
European Wave and Tidal Energy Conference (EWTEC)	K2M, SINTEF, WavEC	Academia, Research Institutes, and Industry Researchers	1,000
ETIP Ocean workshop	K2M	EU Public Authorities	400
International Conference on Ocean Energy (ICOE)	WavEC, Hydman, AW-Energy	Industry developers, Policymakers, Investors, Academia, Research Institutes, and Industry Researchers	100
Offshore Energy Exhibition & Conference	Hydman	Key decision-makers such as Industry developers, Policymakers, and Investors.	12,000
Ocean Energy Europe	SINTEF	Industry developers, Policymakers, and Investors.	400
European Safety and Reliability Conference (ESREL)	VTT	Academia, Research Institutes, and Industry Researchers	500
Probabilistic Safety Assessment & Management conference (PSAM)	VTT	Academia, Research Institutes, and Industry Researchers	1,000
International Conference on Coastal Engineering	UiB	Academia, Research Institutes, and Industry Researchers	2,000
International Joint Conference on Neural Networks	LIN	Academia, Research Institutes, and Industry Researchers	400

6 WHO: INDIVIDUAL DISSEMINATION PLANS FOR PARTNERS

Each partner has its separate dissemination plan, and these are as shown in Table 6-1 Overview of individual dissemination plans during MegaRoller.

Table 6-1 Overview of individual dissemination plans during MegaRoller

Partner	Activities during the project phase
AWE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organize two MegaRoller workshops that will showcase MegaRoller PTO and demonstrate its operation in the test bench (first workshop for WEC and renewable energy technology developers interested in technology transfer at M28, a second workshop for potential customers, members of standards working groups, government representatives and press at M32). Give three talks in the most influential future energy events, e.g. World Energy Congress, The Future of Energy Summit, The Energy Executive Forum. Publish a conference paper in International Conference on Ocean Energy in 2020. Publish press releases when significant project milestones are reached.
ABB	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Present project on ABB Power magazine and also through global ABB web site. Publish result as a reference on Renewable Energy Technology on ABB Groups global organization on energy technology seminars and also on the global publication ABB Review.
K2M (Formerly Cruz Acheson)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Attend one conference per year, including publishing a conference paper or presentation. Key industry conferences during the project include the European Wave and Tidal Energy Conference (EWTEC) in Naples in 2019 or the International Conference on Ocean Energy (ICOE) in Washington in 2020. Link with the relevant activities related to standardisation work – preliminarily identified platforms may include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The SET ocean energy implementation plan (including Actions 1.6 Standards and guidelines for evaluation of wave energy technologies or 3.1 Development of certification and standards to support the offshore renewable technology sector). Activities under e.g. the ETIP Ocean events (cf. e.g. Research Priorities 2.2 Increase yield with improved PTO or 2.3 Validation of components and sub-systems).
WavEC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Description of the project in WavEC's website and previous activities carried out by WavEC in the context of the WaveRoller technology development in Peniche. (ongoing). 1 journal paper on the LCA results for the MegaRoller final device and comparison with other MRE technologies and other means of electricity generation, to be published in a marine renewable energy dedicated (e.g., Marine Renewable Energy Journal). 1 conference paper on EIA standard methods for nearshore wave energy

	<p>devices in ICOE or EWTEC conferences, respectively.</p>
Hydroll	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participate in at least 3 marine industry events such as the Offshore Energy Exhibition & Conference, International Conference on Ocean Energy and Ocean Energy Europe Events.
Hydman	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participate in at least 3 marine industry events such as the Offshore Energy Exhibition & Conference, International Conference on Ocean Energy and Ocean Energy Europe Events.
SINTEF	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publish 1 journal paper "Grid Integration of wave energy farms: Modeling and simulation" at the end of the project, and 1 conference paper per year or presentations per year (reaching 300+ researchers). • Organize a scientific dissemination event at M18 targeting the marine energy research community. • Speak at marine energy European events such as European Wave and Tidal Energy Conference (EWTEC) and Ocean Energy Europe (OEE). If possible, organize a specific project-related session between M30 and M36.
VTT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publish 1 journal paper in an international renewable energy sector journal, 2 conference papers on international ESREL and PSAM conferences and 1 paper in the national Automation day conference.
UiB	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publish 2 journal papers and 1 conference paper. • Present the results at the ICCE (International Conference on Coastal Engineering) in 2020.
LIN	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poster contribution at the 27th Annual Computational Neuroscience Meeting in Seattle/US (July 13 -- July 18, 2018): A. Matysiak A. Hajizadeh, N. Härtwich, R. König, P. May: "A mechanistic model explains auditory evoked responses as a reflection of network properties of the entire auditory cortex". • Poster at Bernstein Conference in Berlin/Germany (September 25 -- September 28, 2018): Aida Hajizadeh, Artur Matysiak, Asim H. Dar, Nina Härtwich, Patrick J. C. May, Reinhard König: "Auditory event-related fields emerging from the network structure of the auditory cortex". • Publish 2 open-access journal papers: one on the machine-learning results of the project (International Journal of Neural Systems) and the other on predictive processing in auditory cortex (PLoS Computational Biology). • Present the results at the International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN) and publish related conference papers.

7 WHEN: TIME PLAN FOR DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

The Dissemination Plan describes relevant activities that will be undertaken to accomplish the goals mentioned above. However, dissemination activities will be done continuously during the project. The time plan for dissemination can be divided into three phases:

- Initial phase. In this phase the main goal is to establish the dissemination plan in M6 which includes the activities, tools, and procedures to facilitate the dissemination process. No specific dissemination output is expected but some dissemination processes will have started, e.g planning of publications and interface for open publications. The website is established and released. It was important to finish the building of the website at an early stage in order to make dissemination information on the project and the partners available.
- Intermediate phase. In this phase, the dissemination will focus on creating awareness of the progress in the project. Specific dissemination outputs are expected. The first workshop for WEC and renewable energy technology developers interested in technology transfer is expected. The project video will be produced at the end of the phase. A dissemination report will be released in M18.
- Final phase: In the final stage, most of the dissemination results and output will be ready. The second workshop for potential customers, members of standards working groups, government representatives and press is expected to be held. The final dissemination report will be released in M44.

Table 7-1 shows a timeline of the activities in the above-mentioned stages. It is quite clear that a time plan is indicative as it will have to fit with external events, the current needs of the project, maturity of results produced and availability of stakeholders. An outline of such is illustrated below. These periods are indicative only.

Table 7-1 Timeplan for dissemination

Task	2018			2019				2020				2021		
	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	
	Initial Phase			Intermediate phase							Final phase			
Publications	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
Workshops							x						x	
Reporting		x					x						x	
Video					(x)*				x					
Standardization							x						x	

8 SUMMARY

Table 8-1 summarizes the dissemination plan with the various related activities, who, how and why.

Table 8-1 Summary of the Dissemination plan

What	Where	By Whom	How	To Whom	Why
Website	URL domain https://www.sintef.no/MegaRoller Project period 3 years	SINTEF is responsible for the website	Uploading open-access material or link to material available.	All the stakeholders	Increased awareness of the MegaRoller project. Show progress and main results Advertise events
Conference presentations and posters	Suitable events	All MegaRoller partners (details in the above section)	Writing papers in relevant events Giving speeches at relevant events	Participants of the events	Shared/Transfer Knowledge in the research community
Scientific publications	Suitable publication	All MegaRoller partners (details in above section)	Submitting paper in relevant publications	All the stakeholders especially researchers	Shared/Transfer Knowledge in the research community
Standardization	Working group reports	AW-Energy	Writing reports	All the stakeholders especially members of standards working groups	Transfer Experience with other developers
End-user workshops	AW-Energy facilities	AW-Energy	Presentations, a tour of facilities and Q&A sessions	All the stakeholders especially potential customers, members of standards working groups and government representatives and press	Demonstration of MegaRoller
Project Video	Web	SINTEF	Producing a project video	All the stakeholders especially broader audience	Inform the broader audience about the project concept

9 DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES SINCE M1

Dissemination activities are related both to the individual partners and to the consortium as a whole. In this section it is described a summary of the activities and the related channels, and the key publications made by the MegaRoller consortium.

9.1 Website

The project website (www.megaroller.eu) is used for communicating results and linking to relevant dissemination material, news and blogs. A [project fact sheet](#) has been produced and is available for download via the dissemination link at the project website.

Figure 2 Screenshot from the MegaRoller website

The website is the main portal for users to find publication of informational material, partner information, scientific papers, blogs, and link open deliverables/publications. More information about the website can be found in the D6.15 Communications report II.

9.2 Scientific publications

A number of scientific journal papers, conference papers, conference posters and talks have been produced in the project.

9.2.1 Peer reviewed papers

1. Hajizadeh, A., Matysiak, A., May, P.J.C. et al: Explaining event-related fields by a mechanistic model encapsulating the anatomical structure of auditory cortex., Biological Cybernetics, Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Issue 3, pp 321-345, 2019

2. Aida Hajizadeh, Artur Matysiak, Andre Brechmann, Reinhard König, Patrick J.C May: Why do humans have unique auditory event-related fields: Evidence from computational modelling and MEG experiments, Wiley Online Library
3. Maria Apolonia, Teresa Simas; Life Cycle Assessment of an Oscillating Wave Surge Energy Converter, Journal of Marine Science and Engineering, MDPI, 17 February 2021
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9.2.2 Conference papers, Posters, Conference talks

13. Preliminary validation of a 1MW oscillating wave surge converter WECsim model P. Laporte Weywada, J. Cruz, J. Scriven, M. Vuorinen, and T. Maki, EWTEC 2019 (paper)
14. Introducing non-rigid body structural dynamics to WEC-Sim J. Scriven, P. Laporte-Weywada, J. Cruz; EWTEC 2019 (talk)
15. “A mechanistic model explains auditory evoked responses as a reflection of network properties of the entire auditory cortex”. 27th Annual Computational Neuroscience Meeting in Seattle/US, July 13 – 18, 2018: Matysiak A. Hajizadeh, N. Härtwich, R. König, P. May: (poster)

16. "Auditory event-related fields emerging from the network structure of the auditory cortex". Bernstein Conference in Berlin/Germany, Sept. 25 – 28, 2018: Aida Hajizadeh, Artur Matysiak, Asim H. Dar, Nina Härtwich, Patrick J. C. May, Reinhard König: (poster)
17. "Neural network model of auditory cortex and its potential application for ocean wave-to-wave prediction". University of Bergen/Norway, Oct. 25, 2018: Artur Matysiak: (invited talk)
18. "Auditory event-related fields emerging from the network structure of the auditory cortex". (poster). International Workshop on Dynamics of Coupled Oscillator Systems at Weiherstrass Institute for Applied Analysis and Stochastics, Berlin/Germany, Nov. 19 – 21, 2018: Aida Hajizadeh, Artur Matysiak, Asim H. Dar, Nina Härtwich, Patrick May, Reinhard König:
19. "Mathematical Modeling and Simulation": Leibniz Network MMS-Days at Leibniz Institute for Atmospheric Physics, Kühlungsborn/Germany, Mar. 20 – 22, 2019: Artur Matysiak, Patrick J.C. May, Reinhard König: "Combining machine learning with auditory neuroscience for predicting ocean waves in a green-energy project". (poster)
20. "Adaptation in auditory cortex explained as a modulation of the network dynamics of coupled damped harmonic oscillators". Bernstein Conference in Berlin/Germany, Sept. 18 – 20, 2019: Aida Hajizadeh, Artur Matysiak, Matthias Wolfrum, Patrick J. C. May, Reinhard König: (poster)
21. "Neural adaptation in auditory cortex is a complex network phenomenon: preliminary results from simulations and intra-cortical measurements". Bernstein Conference in Berlin/Germany, Sept. 18 – 20, 2019: Nina Härtwich, Jing Ma, Matthias Deliano, Reinhard König, Patrick J. C. May: (poster)
22. Ocean Energy Europe in Dublin/Ireland, Sept. 30 – Oct. 1, 2019
 - a. J Åkerberg : The MegaRoller project: Challenges and new developments (talk)
 - b. J.C. May : Applying auditory neuroscience in energy production (talk)
 - c. Til K Vrana : Wave power: Levelized value of Energy (talk)
 - d. M Apolonia : Dividing on best environmental monitoring practices in wave energy (talk)
 - e. C Ridgewell : Making Wave Energy bankable / Final Assembly of a first commercial WaveRoller (talk)
 - f. MegaRoller side event; event organizer/chair: SINTEF, Hans Christian Bolstad
23. "Developing an Environmental Impact Assessment model for nearshore wave energy devices". EWTEC 2019, M Apolonia, A Silva and T. Simas (poster)
24. "WaveRoller Technology", Christopher Ridgewell; Advanced Clean Energy Summit 2019, ACES 2019, Sep 17th 2019, Denver Colorado American Society of Mechanical Engineers (ASME).
25. "Technologies, value chains and materials for Renewable Energy Systems", Christopher Ridgewell SET Plan 2019 Session A.1, 14.11.2019, Helsinki.
26. "The ocean as a renewable energy source". Green connections San Diego, 21-11-2019, Christopher Ridgewell.
27. Recharge Annual Thought Leaders' summit, Copenhagen 25.11-2019. Invited talk Christopher Ridgewell.

28. "EIA preliminary model for nearshore wave energy devices", INORE 2018. Maria Apolonia, Theresa Simas; (poster) 22.-27.10.2019 Scotland
29. "Introducing non-rigid body structural dynamics". J. Scriven, P. Laporte-Weywada, J. Cruz EWTEC19, 1-6 September 2019.
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32. "Investigating the formation of a memory trace: adaptation in the auditory cortex"; Bernstein Conference 2020: Nina Härtwich, Jing Ma, Artur Matysiak, Michael G. K. Brunk, Matthias Deliano, Max F. K. Happel, Frank W. Ohl, Eike Budinger, Reinhard König, Patrick J. C. May; 29/9-2/10-2020
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34. "Performance vs. Survivability: Evaluation of a Range of Control Strategies in a 1MW Oscillating Wave Surge Converter (OWSC)", Pauline Laporte Weywada, Joshua Scriven, Artur Matysiak, Reinhard Koenig, Patrick May, Volker Roeber, Henrik Kalisch, Proceedings of the European Wave and Tidal Energy Conference, EWTEC 2021, Online 8/9 2021
35. "Grid Connection and system services of a wave power plant – a case study"; Vrana, T.K, Åkerberg, J, Flynn D, Torres-Olguin R., Proceedings of the European Wave and Tidal Energy Conference, EWTEC 2021, Online Conference 9/9 2021

9.2.3 Open deliverables

The following project official deliverables have been/will be made public through Zenodo as soon as they are finally approved:

<u>Del no</u>	<u>Title</u>
---------------	--------------

D1.1	Advanced wave-structure interaction WEC model – theory and user manual
D1.2	Definition of priority DLCs and loads characterisation report
D1.3	Near shore wave-forecasting model – theory and user manual
D1.7	Loads model: verification, pre-validation and validation report
D2.6	Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) and Socio-Economic Impact Assessment (SEIA) models
D5.1	Validation methodology and plans
D5.2	Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) and Socio-Economic Impact Assessment (SEIA) of the MegaRoller device
D5.3	Final LCA report of the MegaRoller device
D6.2	Innovation management plan

- D6.3 Dissemination plan
- D6.5 Data management plan
- D6.6 Standards gap analysis
- D6.7 Communication report I
- D6.8 Dissemination report I
- D6.11 LCOE report
- D6.12 Business cases
- D6.13 Standardization report
- D6.14 Data management report
- D6.15 Communication report II
- D6.16 Dissemination report II
- D6.19 Data management update
- D7.5 Final (Public) Report

9.3 Industry events/conferences

Industry events are key to observing the status of the industry and meeting with relevant stakeholders. Some key events and the participation groups are described in Table 5-2 MegaRoller participation events.

ICOE 2018

The International Conference on Ocean Energy; ICOE, took place in Cherbourg, France on June 12th to June 14th, 2018. MegaRoller Coordinator Tuula Mäki presented at the International Conference of Ocean Engineering in France the MegaRoller project as part of the presentation with the title: [WaveRoller Showcase](#).

Figure 3 Tuula Mäki, AW Energy Oy speaking at ICOE 2018 plenary session in Normandie, France

The International Conference on Ocean Energy (ICOE) is a global marine energy event focused on the industrial development of renewable marine energy. Held every two years, the goal of the conference and exhibition is to share recent experiences from research and demonstration efforts. It aims to accelerate development by stimulating collaboration networks between companies and research and

development centres. It has a separate exhibition area and attracts scientists, developers, public authorities and funding organizations. At the 2018 event there were 3 500 participants, 36 countries; +220 exhibitors; 140 international speakers; 65 research posters and 33 conference sessions.

A blog about the MegaRoller participation in this event was published on the MegaRoller website: <https://www.sintef.no/en/events/archive/2018/icoe-the-international-conference-on-ocean-energy-june-2018/>

OEE 2019

Ocean Energy Europe is organizing the OEE conferences. This industry association represents ocean energy in Europe and Ocean Energy Europe is also the largest network of ocean energy professionals in the world. Over 120 organisations, including Europe's leading utilities, industrialists, and research institutes, are members. OEE is organized every 2nd year.

The 2019 OEE event took place in Dublin on the 30th of September to 1st October <https://www.oceanenergy-europe.eu/annual-event/oee2019/> and attracted around 450 participants and over 200 organizations from all over the world. A significant number of participants came from Island regions representing user groups that can be expected to be early adopters of wave energy farms. The OEE is primarily a conference but also hosts an exhibition with 60 exhibitors.

MegaRoller hosted its own side event at the OEE 2019. The program was informed through the event program, event web and roll up placed in the exhibition area. The side event sign-up/participation list shows 50+ participants (not published for GDPR reasons) from various industries and stakeholder categories, including financial, political, engineering, and WEC suppliers, and came from Belgium, Denmark, Finland, France, Ireland, Italy, Monaco, Norway, Portugal, Singapore, Sweden, Spain, and the United Kingdom.

The screenshot shows the OEE 2019 event website. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links: Home, About Ocean Energy, About OEE, Policy & Advocacy, OEE2019, Events, and a search icon. Below this is a secondary navigation bar with links: OEE2019, Exhibition, Programme, Vi Maris Award, Registration, Practical info, Side Events, and SEAI. The main content area features a large banner with the text "REGISTER NOW" in large green letters, followed by "30 SEPTEMBER 1 OCTOBER 2019 DUBLIN, IRELAND". Below this, it says "Supported by" and lists "OCEAN ENERGY EUROPE" and "seai SUSTAINABLE ENERGY AUTHORITY OF IRELAND". At the bottom left, there is a logo for "IRENA + IRENA Event on 1 - 2 Oct". On the right side of the banner, there is a box titled "About the event" with the following text: "Date : 30 September, 2019 - 1 October, 2019", "Location : CCD, Dublin, Ireland", and "The annual Ocean Energy Europe Conference & Exhibition is the meeting point for the whole ocean energy sector." Below this text are two green buttons: "PROGRAMME" and "EXHIBITORS LIST". The background of the banner shows a large yellow crane on a ship's deck over the ocean.

Figure 4 From the OEE event web page informing of the MegaRoller side event in 2019

Programme

The MegaRoller project: Challenges and new developments
Jussi Åkerberg, CTO AW-Energy Oy

Applying auditory neuroscience in energy production
Patrick J. C. May, PhD/Reader, Lancaster University

Wavepower – leveled value of energy
Til Kristian, Vrana, PhD/Researcher, SINTEF

Deciding on best environmental monitoring practices in wave energy
Maria Apolonia, MSc/Researcher, WaveEC

Final Assembly of a first commercial WaveRoller
Christopher Ridgewell, CEO AW-Energy Oy

There will be a Q&A session at the end of the event.

Figure 5 The OEE 2019 side event program information

OEE 2019 impressions: Top left; From the OEE exhibition area.

Lower left and right: Maria Apolonia (WaveEC) and Jussi Åkerberg (AW-Energy) during their presentations of MegaRoller – LCA analysis tools and the Challenges and new Developments, respectively at the MegaRoller Side Event at the conference.

The list of talks is shown under conference and journal papers (see section 9.2).

9.4 Standardization work

Communicating results and outcomes of relevance to the standardization groups in Europe and the world is work being undertaken in task 6.6 of MegaRoller. A gap analysis report (D6.6) was issued earlier and the MegaRoller project is following up on through reviews and feedback to the following standardization groups:

IEC/TC 62600-2 – Electricity producing wave energy converters – Design requirements for marine energy systems, expected in 2020

PD IEC/TS 6200-40 Ed- 1 Marine Energy – Wave, tidal and other water current converters. Part 40. Acoustic characterization of marine energy converters.

The participation in the standardization bodies has and have the following purposes:

- Review of existing standards and guidelines
 - IEC technical specifications (specifically IEC TC 114)
 - Standards (DNV, API, NORSOK...)
 - Collect input from consortium to generate feedback to the standards committees
- Identify requirements
 - Technology assessment
 - prioritize risk mitigation
- Highlight salient gaps

With the following goals:

- Ensure that the design and testing efforts in MegaRoller are conducted in adherence with standards
- Document real-case application of relevant standards and guidelines
- Use connections to standardisation groups to disseminate MegaRoller findings to Marine Energy community including members of ETIP Ocean.

K2 Management has participated in the standardization meetings and has issued 2 deliverables on the standardization aspects of MegaRoller, D6.6 Standards gap analysis and D6.13 Standardization report.

9.5 Tutorials and educational materials

9.5.1 Scientific blogs

The following scientific blogs with MegaRoller topics have been made available at www.megaroller.eu.

Identifying key environmental effects of wave energy deployments

Maria Apolonia and Teresa Simas, WavEC:

As technology evolves towards commercial scale, potential environmental impacts of wave energy deployments have been gaining more and more attention over the last years, from both developers and regulators. The fact that wave energy projects have unique characteristics, different from any other marine projects, results in a lack of methodological approaches for environmental and socio-economic impacts evaluation. Current existing levels of uncertainty in the sector pose a major problem to the accurate identification of key environmental effects and subsequent steps of an Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA), such as the elaboration of monitoring plans.

In other words, a key environmental effect is the result of the interaction between a receptor and a stressor.

The result of this exercise is an impact matrix similar to the one shown below. These key effects are then evaluated through a ranking classification criterion (the one shown in the example was adapted from EMEC guidelines). Such an approach allows for the developer to get the 'big picture' of all the potential impacts across all development phases and to choose which ones to focus the mitigation measures on.

Biological Effects			Receptor							
Development phase	Activity	Stressor	Benthic Communities		Fish & Turtles		Marine Mammals		Birds	
			Key Effect	Mag	Key Effect	Mag	Key Effect	Mag	Key Effect	Mag
Preparation	Surveying	Sampling: coring, boring and grab sampling	Loss of biodiversity	Yellow	NK	Grey	NK	Grey	NK	Grey
		Noise from Vessels and sonar/seismic surveys	Disruption of behaviour; potential harm	Orange	Disruption of behaviour; potential harm	Orange	Disruption of behaviour; potential harm	Orange	Disruption of behaviour	Green
	Site preparation	Dredging Activities	Productivity reduction; loss of biodiversity; food web implications	Orange	Disruption of behaviour; food web implications	Yellow	Disruption of behaviour; food web implications	Yellow	Disruption of behaviour; food web implications	Yellow
Construction	Transport of wave device and support structures	Vessel activity; Presence of machinery/equipment	Disruption of behaviour	Yellow	Disruption of behaviour	Yellow	Disruption of behaviour	Yellow	Disruption of behaviour	Yellow
		Noise from vessels	Disruption of behaviour; potential harm	Yellow	Disruption of behaviour; potential harm	Yellow	Disruption of behaviour; potential harm	Yellow	Disruption of behaviour	Yellow
	Installation of wave device and support structures	Installation of WEC; Piling/drilling activities	Productivity reduction; Loss of Biodiversity; Food web implications	Orange	Disruption of behaviour; food web implications	Yellow	Disruption of behaviour; food web implications	Yellow	Disruption of behaviour	Yellow
		Noise from piling/drilling activities	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm	Orange	Disruption of behaviour; potential harm	Orange	Disruption of behaviour; potential harm	Orange	Disruption of behaviour	Orange

Figure 6 From the blog on environmental effects studied in MegaRoller

Wave vs. Wind and Solar; Levelised Value of Energy

Til Kristian Vrana, SINTEF Energy Research:

This blog discusses the hypothesis that wave power can deliver more value than wind and solar due to its availability when market prices are generally higher. Wave power does not follow a clear day-night pattern (unlike solar power), but it has a clear summer-winter pattern: the waves are larger in the winter. This is positively correlated with the fact that electricity prices often are higher during the winter (less solar power, more load).

Figure 7 Seasonal power fluctuations. From the blog "Wave vs. Wind and Solar – Levelised Value of Energy"

Applying Auditory Neuroscience to Wave Energy Models

Patrick May, Lancaster University [formerly from Leibnitz university]

This blog describes one of the development activities in the MegaRoller project that is probably a very novel feature which is linked to the ability to predict the height of future waves. This prediction is essential to design an efficient ocean wave energy system. And to tackle this problem MegaRoller researchers turned to a surprising form of inspiration: the human auditory system.

Wave Energy: The Standardisation of the Industry

Pauline Laporte Weywada, K2M

This blog discusses the critical gaps and needs of the WEC industry regarding what standards are available for the development of the industry, what are the gaps – or missing aspects – what are the next steps for further standardisation work and how MegaRoller can contribute to the development of the standards in this industry.

IEC

TECHNICAL SPECIFICATION

Modelling Wave Behaviour to Maximise Wave Power Generation

Henrik Kalisch and Volker Roeber, University of Bergen;

This MegaRoller project blog post was written by Henrik Kalisch, University of Bergen, Volker Roeber, Université de Pau et des Pays de l'Adour, E2S-UPPA, chair HPC-Waves, SIAME and University of Bergen.

Just as a weather forecast can accurately predict rainfall for a city but not on which streets it will fall, many existing ocean models are less accurate close to the shore. As part of the MegaRoller wave energy research project, the University of Bergen has improved a model to better predict wave behaviour close to shore.

Figure 8 Snapshot of the ocean surface after 90 min of computation showing wave crests and troughs from an incoming swell with 1.5m significant wave height and 15 sec peak period.

9.5.2 Educational and scientific videos

The scientific videos are in a format where a presenter talks through a specific topic as in a panel and webinar style setting. These videos are primarily targeted at the engineering teams, scientific and academic groups and ocean energy companies and their duration is about 10-15 minutes.

Table 9-1 Overview of educational videos. All are published at www.MegaRoller.eu

Video	Topic and main presenter	Duration
	<p>System approach to reliability engineering – case wave energy converter</p> <p>Risto Tiusanen, VTT</p>	13:10
	<p>Performance vs. survivability for different control strategies</p> <p>Pauline Laporte Weywada, K2 Management</p>	12:37
	<p>Life Cycle Cost (LCC) in perspective of wave energy</p> <p>Minna Räikkönen, VTT</p>	20:44
	<p>Developments of a phase-resolving wave model - To support WEC applications</p> <p>Henrik Kalisch, University of Bergen,</p>	12.24

Video	Topic and main presenter	Duration
<p>IMPROVING THE ENVIRONMENTAL ACCEPTANCE OF WAVE ENERGY TOOLS APPLIED IN MEGAROLLER</p> <p>Maria Apolonia Project Manager, WavEC - Offshore Renewables</p> <p>MegaRoller</p>	<p>Improving the environmental acceptance of wave energy – Tools applied in MegaRoller</p> <p>Maria Apolonia, Wavec</p>	<p>11:00</p>
<p>Lancaster Psychology Research Showcase Series</p> <p>Lancaster University</p> <p>Harnessing auditory neuroscience for green energy production</p> <p>June 22nd 2021 Speaker: Dr. Patrick May Host: Dr. Daphne Barker</p>	<p>"Harnessing auditory neuroscience for green energy production" by Dr Patrick May</p> <p>https://youtu.be/3l70aJK03_U</p>	<p>47:07</p>

9.5.3 Use of Zenodo

Zenodo is the chosen portal /repository and user interface for open publications by the project. MegaRoller has established its own user area / community in Zenodo; see Figure 9. At this repository external users can download relevant material made public by the project. The direct link is <https://zenodo.org/communities/763959>

The screenshot shows the Zenodo website interface. At the top, there is a search bar and navigation tabs for 'Upload' and 'Communities'. The main content area is titled 'MegaRoller' and displays 'Recent uploads'. There are four upload entries listed, each with a date, version number, and a 'View' button. The entries are:

- D6.11 LCOE Report** (May 6, 2021, v1) by Nyman, Mikko; Åkerberg, Jussi; Pech, Matthew; Vuorinen, Matti.
- D5.3 Final LCA report of the MegaRoller device** (January 29, 2020, 3.0) by Apolonia, Maria.
- D5.2 Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) and Socio-Economic Impact Assessment (SEIA) of the MegaRoller device** (January 29, 2021, 3.0) by Vinagre, Pedro; Apolonia, Maria.
- D5.1 Validation methodology and plans** (May 24, 2021, v1) by Tiisanen, Risto; Sarsama, Janne; Apolonia, Maria; Vinagre, Pedro; Rääkkönen, Minna; Heikkilä, Eetu; Väälä, Tero; Raunio, Kalle; Pasanen, Sami.

The right sidebar contains a 'New upload' button, the MegaRoller logo, and project details:

- Community:** MegaRoller
- Description:** This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 763959. The MegaRoller Project will develop and demonstrate a Power Take-Off for wave energy converters.
- Key Metrics:**
 - Starting date: May 1st 2018
 - Project duration: 36 months
 - EU Contribution: EUR 4,946,768
 - Number of partners: 10
 - Coordinator: Hydroll OY
- Curated by:** lailaa
- Curation policy:** MegaRoller Scientific publications: If published in Open Access Journals, upload published Version of article, else upload accepted Version.
- MegaRoller Research data:** Upload only Research data with Access Level "Public".
- Created:** July 3, 2018

Figure 9 Screenshot from the MegaRoller Zenodo site

Zenodo supports download and user statistics. As a sample on Zenodo, the following user statistics can be shown for the report on the Advanced Wave-Structure interaction model manual.

October 24, 2018

Project deliverable Open Access

D1.1 Advanced Wave-Structure Interaction Model – Theory and User Manual

Laporte Weywada, Pauline

This document constitutes a theory and user manual of the MegaRoller wave energy converter (WEC) model developed under WP1 in a custom version of the numerical simulation package WEC-Sim. The present deliverable is the main output of Task 1.2, aiming to define and develop a nonlinear model of the MegaRoller WEC to assess the influence of the distributed loading contributions over the WEC prime mover, i.e. the flap, accounting for the coupled nature of interaction(s) between the flap and the power take-off (PTO) load sources. The outputs of Task 1.2 aim to support the design process to be conducted in WP2.

This document describes the fundamental theory associated with the WEC-Sim model and the essential aspects related to its practical use. In essence, the developed model aims to enable the estimation of hydrodynamic, structural and all relevant mechanical loads for devices that involve rigid bodies, PTO systems and moorings. Simulations are performed in the time-domain by solving the governing WEC equations of motion in all relevant degrees-of-freedom, in a fully-coupled format (i.e. simultaneously accounting for all relevant load sources). WEC models are constructed on a multi-body basis. This approach allows a WEC to be constructed by linking together a number of constituent bodies, representing different physical entities in the machine. Each body must incorporate one or more components, which are used to describe the key WEC characteristics. Multi-body modelling allows a wide range of WEC concepts to be modelled using a consistent, fully-coupled engineering code.

The description of the code functionalities is supported by a preliminary validation exercise, using the previous design iteration of the WaveRoller WEC as tested in the Queen's University of Belfast between August 2017 and January 2018 (see e.g. <http://aw-energy.com/news/awe-and-queens-university-belfast-finish-waveroller-tank-tests/>). The pre-validation exercise showed good comparisons in terms of PTO torque and prime mover motion in pitch, both for regular and irregular waves.

However, it is recognised that development work on the WEC-Sim model of the MegaRoller WEC will continue throughout the course of the MegaRoller project. As a consequence, the theoretical formulation and practical aspects here described are subject to future updates. In particular, it is envisaged that the consideration of a number of further nonlinear effects relevant for large structure such as the MegaRoller WEC will be required, potentially leading to changes in the core formulation and the introduction of novel / updated features. Such nonlinear effects may include the consideration of fluid-structure interactions, or slap and slam loads. Some of these initial features are also introduced in this report, guiding the development of the MegaRoller WEC-Sim model to be conducted in Task 1.3.

22 views
16 downloads
[See more details...](#)

Publication date:
October 24, 2018

DOI:
DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.2562765](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2562765)

Keyword(s):
MegaRoller Wave-structure interaction model
WEC-Sim model User manual

Grants:
[European Commission](#)

- MegaRoller - Developing the PTO of the first MW-level Oscillating Wave Surge Converter (763959)

Communities:
[MegaRoller](#)

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Figure 10 Document description in Zenodo

9.6 Dissemination reports

The dissemination overview and reports will show an overview of the various activities planned on and individual organization level and project level. The deliverables planned in this project are presented in the list below.

Report/Deliverable	When	Status
Dissemination Plan	M6	Approved
Dissemination Report	M18	Approved
Dissemination Report II	Project End	This report

9.7 Project videos

After the pandemic, digital media has played a more important role in the dissemination activities and a set of project videos explaining key results – such as the MegaRoller test setup – has been developed to better inform stakeholders and the public community.

A video presenting the project, the content of the work packages, the work package leaders and the key goals of the project is also available on the project website and on YouTube:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=swQDbHCVhPI>

Figure 11 From one of the project videos on YouTube showing Jussi Åkerberg of AW-Energy explaining the key concepts of the MegaRoller project.

Further videos presenting the partners and all the work packages have been filmed and are in processing before release. The videos present all the work package leaders from WP1 to WP6 (AW-Energy being WP lead for both WP2 and WP4).

Figure 12 MegaRoller work package videos

9.7.1 Project feature videos

	<p>A second project feature film has been made in 2 versions: The short version – with duration of 1 minute is primarily a teaser for social media use.</p>
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	<p>The longer version of the video showcases the activities and the partners in the project.</p> <p>Published at www.MegaRoller.eu</p>
	<p>In this popular science video targeting the public audience, CEO Christopher Ridgewell of AW-Energy explains some of the basics of wave energy and the vast potential inherent to it.</p> <p>Published at www.MegaRoller.eu</p>
	<p>The test facility in Vantaa, Finland was a key result of the MegaRoller project.</p> <p>In this video, Sami Pasanen, Technical Manager at AW-Energy, gives a tour to the audience and explains the key features and technical progress in the project to a wider audience.</p> <p>Published at www.MegaRoller.eu</p>

A TV program showcasing the MegaRoller project with EuroNews science channel Futuris was under planning but had to be cancelled due to the pandemic.

9.8 Other dissemination activities

9.8.1 Stakeholder events / workshops

VTT visited AW-Energy's test facility in Järvenpää, Finland to take part in a workshop aimed to define the best ways to utilize the project partner's expertise on instrumentation.

The workshop was held on October 23rd, 2018, at AW-Energy's test facility in Finland, which featured a full-scale Power Take-Off unit (PTO) and a wave machine used to simulate real-world wave conditions to

which the PTO is subjected to. VTT experts were offered an in-depth presentation of the instrumentation of both the wave machine and the PTO during an extensive tour of the facilities.

Figure 13 Järvenpää Test Center, wave machine in the test laboratory in 2018

Participants were excited to see the PTO, the wave machine and the instrumentation as viewing the devices in action helps to understand the requirements and functionalities of the instruments better, providing useful insights for the development work.

The purpose of the workshop was to initiate the design work for the MegaRoller test bench and PTO instrumentation and to define the way VTT instrumentation expertise can be best utilized in the project. This workshop was one in a series of workshops, visits and meetings held to advance the MegaRoller test bench and PTO design work.

A feature film was produced to showcase the new facility for the PTO testing set up and finalized in 2021.

An overview of the test equipment. In the video, each of the technical innovations and functions are presented.

Sami Pasanen, AW-Energy and Hans Christian Bolstad, SINTEF during the interview at the test facility.

Pictures: SINTEF

9.8.2 Press release on the completion of the WEC model

A press release on the completion of the report of the wave energy converter model was issued 08th May 2019 and was reported in relevant topical journals; e.g. [Maritime Journal](#):

The MegaRoller project team has completed an 'advanced custom structure interaction Wave Energy Converter (WEC) model.'

So, what wave energy technology is under development, and what have been the results so far?

WAVE SURGE CONVERTER

To support the wave energy industry in its bid to become a mainstream energy source, the European Commission is funding the MegaRoller project via its Horizon 2020 programme. The project, launched in 2018 and planned for completion in 2021, is seeking to develop and demonstrate a 1MW Power Take-Off (PTO) technology for oscillating wave surge converters (OWSC). As Michael Holm - Chief Marketing & Communications Officer at project partner K2 Management, explains, the MegaRoller project aims to reduce the levelized cost of energy (LCOE) of the system to below 150€/MWh by increasing its PTO capacity, reliability, and efficiency and streamlining the PTO system with standard components.

In doing so, the project team is focusing its efforts on the developments of OWSC technology - a type of wave power technology that generates electricity by exploiting the horizontal movement of waves in near-shore coastal areas, at water depths of 10-20m. Typically, OWSCs use bottom-hinged flaps that oscillate in pitch, following the horizontal motion of the water particles.

"The MegaRoller project specifically focuses on the development of the PTO system - that is, the core component that converts the mechanical power to electricity," says Holm.

DEVELOPMENT AND TESTING

Earlier this year, the project reached an important milestone following the completion of an advanced custom structure interaction Wave Energy Converter (WEC) model. The model was developed to enable a detailed assessment of the distributed loads affecting the MegaRoller WEC system, in an effort to support the PTO design process. It is based on the numerical simulation package WEC-Sim, and contains a number of novel features, including an advanced wave-by-wave control system implementation, the possibility of using a position-dependent

database of hydrodynamic inputs, and the capability to assess the influence directional spectrum in the estimated load patterns. It also includes an advanced structural dynamics module linked to WEC-Sim to enable the consideration of structural deformations of the flap surfaces as a response to the distributed loads on the WEC.

"A preliminary validation exercise was conducted, using the previous WaveRoller design iteration tested in the Queen University of Belfast in 2018," says Holm.

Once the full-scale PTO test rig is completed as part of the MegaRoller project, testing activities will focus on PTO functionality, performance, and power quality, operating the test bench with representative sea states.

Moving forward, Holm reveals that, as the MegaRoller project progresses to the implementation and integration phase, a number of critical aspects are being checked to ensure that the work can progress smoothly.

"This includes the procurement process, with clear specifications, schedule and documentation being prepared to avoid issues in the delivery of the components - and communication between the different project teams to ensure that the components integrate properly with each other," he says.

"Risk levels are consistently monitored throughout the project, in line with best practice, as should be the case with an ambitious and dynamic project of this kind," he adds.

Looking ahead, Holm points out that the next steps of the initiative will involve the completion of the manufacturing drawings, a milestone the project team expects to reach by the end of 2019. Following this, components will be received for assembly of the PTO subsystems and integration of the test rig - including hardware and software.

"This will involve assembly, test commissioning, and validation, including validation of the numerical models developed in our first project milestone. Dissemination activities will also be conducted as the MegaRoller project progresses, involving publication of project results and key findings. The project is currently on track to be completed within the 36-month timescale," adds Holm.

10 FINAL REMARKS

The dissemination activities in the MegaRoller project have been completed with a wide range of publications, blogs and scientific videos. Focus of the dissemination work has been on project visibility while scientific activity has been through technical deliverables, journal publications and conference publications covering the research. A shift of focus to digital format and video was done after COVID-19 pandemic arrived. Additional videos showcasing the test facility and explaining various facts of wave energy in general and key aspects of the research activities have been produced and made available.

The material will be available for many years to come for interested parties. The MegaRoller event organized before the COVID-19 pandemic was very popular, and many contacts in the marine energy community were established - through e.g. the ICOE and OEE conferences - where also Business to Business meetings were conducted.

The MegaRoller project has produced in total over 50 publications and open deliverables from the design and development tasks. The majority of these have been presented in technical journals and at European conferences. Description of the research results and associated informational material has been distributed through the MegaRoller website, Zenodo, YouTube and conference proceedings targeting a wide range of stakeholder groups.